

METAL/CERAMIC COMPOSITE TAPES DEVELOPED FOR HIGH TEMPERATURE SUPERCONDUCTORS

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical properties (stress-strain curves), fracture microstructure and changes of the critical current density vs. bending have been studied for metal/ceramic superconducting composites. This have included both, cold processed and thermally annealed (Bi,Pb)-Sr-Ca-Cu-O high temperature superconductor filled silver sheathed wires, as well as the corresponding empty silver sheaths.

Keywords: high T_c superconductors, Mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the recent development of metal/ceramic (high temperature superconductor, HTS) composites^[1,2] much of the effort has been focused on increasing the critical current density (J_c , maximum value per cross-section that the superconductor may carry without losses). However, there are scarce results on their mechanical properties,^[3-5] which are important for developing practical applications. Inasmuch, magnet coils and other systems based on these composites must work at liquid nitrogen temperatures, in the best case, implying severe mechanical conditions because of the strong Lorentz forces during service and thermal cycling.^[4]

The most encouraging results have so far been obtained with Ag/(Bi,Pb)-Sr-Ca-Cu-O (BSCCO) composite tapes prepared by the Powder-in-Tube (PIT) method.^[1] In this process, HTS powders are packed into Ag-tubes, drawn through a set of diminishing diameter dies, laminated by rolling and axial pressing, and annealed in a furnace for different periods of time at fixed temperatures.^[2] The critical current (I_c) of the bulk wire is the technological parameter to optimise. This value is determined by both, the J_c and the BSCCO core cross section in relation to the total composite wire cross section. Furthermore, appropriate mechanical properties, thermal stability and reliability in the fabrication of these composite wires are required to develop practical superconducting devices. The design of the metal/ceramic composites must be performed considering their mechanical and electrical properties.

In this contribution the mechanical properties of Ag/BSCCO composites have been investigated using tensile strength testing with the aim of giving some insight into their fracture behaviour as well as trying to understand the peculiar BSCCO ceramic grain “plasticity”. The latter facilitates a high degree of grain orientation within the tape’s core^[6] when using the PIT method. Moreover, the variation of J_c with induced mechanical deformation (bending) has also been studied for the composite tapes.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The Ag/BSCCO composites used in all experiments have been prepared by the PIT method.^[2] Well characterized superconducting starting powders, with a majority of BSCCO 2223 nominal stoichiometry (critical temperature of 110 K), prepared by the conventional solid state reaction method were used.^[7] Goodfellow analytic quality Ag tubes of 6 mm external and 4 mm internal diameter were filled with these BSCCO powders or with mixtures of Ag and BSCCO powders. Wires of 0.98 mm diameter were obtained after drawing. The wires were rolled into ≈ 0.16 mm thick x 1.4 mm wide tapes, which were subsequently uniaxially pressed to ca. 4 GPa and annealed at 830 °C to yield 0.08-0.1 mm thick x 2.0-2.5 mm wide tapes with cross section (S) distributions given by $r_{Ag} = S_{Ag}/S_{Total} = 0.755$ and $r_{BSCCO} = 0.245$.

Tensile strength testing has been carried out at room temperature on Ag/BSCCO composite wires and tapes using an INSTRON (8032) universal testing machine at a constant crosshead speed of 0.003 mm/s. A 12.5 mm gauge length extensometer was used to measure the displacement. Stress (σ) - strain (ϵ) curves were obtained up to the breakdown point in order to determine the ductility and yielding resistance, as well as to analyze the fracture. In addition, to obtain more detailed information on the elastic-plastic transition, initial stage σ - ϵ measurements were performed up to 1.6 % deformation.

The microstructure of the wire fracture surfaces has been studied by means of scanning electron microscopy, using a JEOL 6400 SEM equipped with an energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analyzer.

J_c versus bending measurements have been performed on optimized Ag/BSCCO monofilamentary tapes^[2] 25 mm length 80 μ m thickness. Starting powders containing different mixtures of Ag and BSCCO have been used. Tape bending was performed at room temperature by fixing the tapes on insulating circular supports with increasing curvature, $1/R$ (R = radius) and keeping the deformation constant during the strain measurement. The curvature was increased, point by point, up to $1/R = 0.50$ cm⁻¹. The full process was applied to each tape, implying that, between two different bending positions, the tape was immersed in liquid nitrogen and cycled back to room temperature. The characteristic voltage-intensity (V - I) curves were measured at 77 K and zero magnetic field by the four point method, using the typical 1 μ V/cm criteria to define I_c . The aging effects due to this thermal cycling have been found to contribute only slightly to tape deterioration, for the number of cycles (7) involved in the full experiment.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Stress-Strain testing

The characteristic σ - ϵ curves obtained for a pure silver metal and an Ag/BSCCO composite wire, both with the same external diameter of 0.98 mm, are depicted in Fig. 1. Both specimens have almost the same silver wall thickness. In order to heal cracks and relax the local stress induced by drawing, as well as to improve the Ag-BSCCO and BSCCO-BSCCO contacts, both were annealed

during 20 h at 830 °C. The $\sigma(\epsilon)$ curve of the ductile Ag tube differs in the case of the composite, where a more brittle behaviour is observed, incorporating the combined properties of the ceramic core and the sheathed metal. The role of the ceramic is essential in explaining the higher resistance observed for the composite as compared with the behaviour of the empty silver tube. Beyond the very small Ag yield point ($<0.05\%$), the silver deforms plastically, whereas the BSCCO core does so elastically. There is a drastic slope change in the composite $\sigma(\epsilon)$ curve at around 0.25 % of strain reaching a region with much lower slope. The $\sigma(\epsilon)$ differences diminish, even changing their relative positions (not shown in Fig. 1) up to the breakdown point where the silver sheath supports almost the full load. The maximum stress takes place at the breakdown point, with values of σ_{\max} and ϵ_{\max} approaching 160 MPa and 35 %, respectively, in the silver tube, whereas they take values of 135 MPa, 35 % in the Ag /BSCCO wire composite; i.e., within experimental uncertainties, the breakdown takes place essentially at the same strain value.

Figure 1 Room temperature stress-strain curves obtained on a Ag/BSCCO composite wire (dashed line) and on an empty silver tube (continuous line) with the same geometry, obtained by identical cold working and annealing processes.

Estimates of the elastic modulus of the specimens may be obtained from the initial slope for the silver tube, with values for E of 70 ± 5 MPa, and from the $\sigma(\epsilon)$ curves for the Ag and Ag/BSCCO composite, which allow to estimate the value of $E(\text{BSCCO})$ as 110 ± 10 MPa.

The same tensile strength test has been performed on similar wires after drawing without annealing. The cold work process followed increases hardness, and consequently, higher values of σ_{\max} and lower ductility with values of 330 MPa and plastic strain of 0.4 % are obtained. However, the curves are continuous and the behaviour at the breakdown point follows the tendency of the annealed samples. Furthermore, $\sigma(\epsilon)$ curves have also been measured on Ag/BSCCO monofilamentary tapes showing the same behaviour found for annealed wires with $\sigma_{\max} = 128$ MPa and $\epsilon_{\max} = 35\%$. In addition, the same experiment performed in multifilamentary wires^[2] in which $r_{\text{BSCCO}}/r_{\text{Ag}} < 0.1$, yielded similar results.

3.2. Fracture Microstructures

The secondary electron SEM image of the fracture surface is shown in Fig. 2. In agreement with the above description, the aspect of the silver sheath's surface is similar to that typically observed in ductile breakdown with resulting structures associated to the energy absorption. Moreover, the clear cleavage observed on the BSCCO grains shows (001) planes parallel to the deforming load, indicating both, the presence of ceramic grains oriented along the wire, and the brittle nature of the material. Nevertheless, small regions with ductile characteristics are also observed in the Bi-containing spherical precipitate of Fig. 2b. It should be noted, however, that the tensile fracture surface shows a greater orientation than in nondeformed wires cross sections, evidencing the BSCCO orientation achieved through plastic deformation.

Figure 2. Secondary electron SEM micrographs of the fractured surface of a Ag/BSCCO composite wire: (a) x170 and (b) x1000.

The usual smoothness found in the $\sigma(\epsilon)$ curves shown in Fig. 1 are in contrast with the observations on other metal/HTS composite tapes based on Y-Ba-Cu-O (YBCO)^[3] and BSCCO^[5] in

which many drops in stress have been found. This phenomenon, called “multiple cracking”, has been assumed to be caused^[3] by HTS core cracking, and explained as follows: The stress of the composite decreases suddenly after an initial crack; further strain increases the hardness of the surrounding Ag sheath and the load bearing capacity of this region in such a way that the original curve is almost recovered. This process yields composites with the HTS cores broken in progressively shorter segments.^[5]

Not only the experimental results presented here for similar composites are in contradiction with the multiple cracking model proposed;^[5] the discrepancy extends to the measured $\sigma(\epsilon)$ curves on the corresponding empty silver wires. If the BSCCO core is fractured at a given section, the total Ag cross-section would support the full load. For the wires studied here, this would amount to a reduction of about 25 % of the initial area. Analysis of the $\sigma(\epsilon)$ curves indicates that, for a fixed strain value above the yielding points, the stress on the composite is more than twice the stress of the empty silver, and the core cracking event would imply either an abrupt jump to lower stress or the breakdown in the composite specimen. The different shapes of the specimens and the unknown thickness of the Ag tape sheath used by Osamura *et al*^[5] preclude further analysis.

In spite of the different stresses induced by drawing, it has been assumed that the silver has the same properties in the composite and in the empty wire. However, the identical annealing treatment used should insure the relaxation of any generated internal stress in both types of samples, and thus a similar soft mechanical behaviour.

Figure 3. Normalized critical current (I_c) at 77 K, as a function of the curvature bending for Ag/BSCCO composite tapes. The maximum curvature corresponds to a strain bending $\epsilon = (100 \delta/2R)$ of 0.15 %. Different amounts of Ag have been mixed with the BSCCO powder: 0 wt % (open circles), 10 wt % (triangles) and 20 wt % (full circles).

3.3. Bending properties

The brittle characteristics of the BSCCO ceramic core may be diminished without decreasing J_c by the addition of varying amounts of powdered Ag into the initial powders.^[6] The added Ag appears as precipitates sandwiched between the BSCCO grains in the ceramic core, and a more ductile

behavior is expected for this configuration. This should permit higher curvature bending and lower aging, facilitating, for example, the winding of the tape to form coils. Normalized values of the critical current for tapes containing different Ag concentrations are represented for different bendings in Fig. 3. These values have been normalized with respect to the values of I_{c0} (9.55 A for 0 wt % Ag; 9.31 A for 10 wt % Ag and 6.04 A for 20 wt % Ag) measured before bending.

In the monofilamentary tapes there is an onset bending radius at which I_c/I_{c0} deteriorates.^[8,9] This onset value depends on the BSCCO thickness (δ) and in the present case (maximum δ is about 60 μm) and for pure ceramics, becomes already important at $R \approx 5$ cm, in agreement with values so far reported.^[8,9] However, it also depends on the Ag-sheath thickness and distribution, diminishing for multifilamentary tapes.^[10]

The dispersion of Ag in the ceramic core, for the same δ , improves the bending characteristics of the BSCCO (2223) based tapes significantly, reproducing previous results.^[11] Moreover, the best bending properties are obtained on tapes containing 10 wt % Ag and, at the same time, these amounts of silver do not decrease I_{c0} . It is then possible, using a different approach, to improve the flexibility of the tapes without decreasing I_c .

4. CONCLUSIONS

From the stress-strain curves obtained on composite Ag/BSCCO wires, monofilamentary and multifilamentary tapes, the breakdown of the core and the silver sheath take place simultaneously, discarding the presence of multiple cracking of the type described by Osamura *et al*^[5] and being determined by the silver sheath. The elastic modulus of the BSCCO ceramic has been estimated as 110 ± 10 MPa. The experiments also confirm the inherent BSCCO deformability due to the structural weakness in the crystallographic *c*-axis direction, which results in (001) plane orientated grains along the uniaxial tensile load.

The inclusion of Ag in the ceramic core (up to 10-20 weight %) improves the bending strain tolerance of the tapes, allowing a curvature radius of 2-2.5 cm (maximum bending strain of 0.15 %) without a decrease in the total critical intensity at 77 K.

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